

CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASE RISK FACTORS OF NORMAL WISTAR RATS ON PROLONGED EXPOSURE TO AQUEOUS STEM BARK EXTRACT OF *DIALIUM GUINEENSE*

***¹Abu, O.D., ²Awhin, E.P. and ³Ekugum, E.**

¹*Department of Biochemistry, Faculty of Life Sciences, University of Benin, Benin City, Nigeria.*

²*Department of Medical Biochemistry, Faculty of Basic Medical Sciences, Delta State University, Abraka, Delta State, Nigeria.*

³*Department of Pharmaceutical Technology, Edo State Polytechnic, Usen, Edo State, Nigeria.*

***Corresponding Email address:** osahon.abu@uniben.edu

Phone Number: +2347086427636

LIVEDNA ID: 234.34827

ORCID: 0000-0002-8007-2199

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17185141>

Keywords:

*Atherogenic index,
Cardiac disease,
Lipids,
Hypercholesterolemia,
Medicinal plant.*

Abstract: *The use of medicinal plants and their products in health management has gained wide acceptance. However, their usage is limited by the inability to ascertain their potential toxic effect at doses administered and duration. The present study investigated the effect of prolonged exposure of normal Wistar rats to aqueous extract of *Dialium guineense* (AEDG) stem bark on cardiovascular disease risk factors. Male albino rats (Wistar strain, n = 10) weighing between 150 and 180 g (mean weight = 165 ± 15 g) were divided into two groups (5 rats per group): control and observation groups. Rats in the observation group received 1000 mg/kg body weight, bwt, AEDG stem bark orally for twelve weeks, and assays were performed on monthly basis. The results showed that exposure of normal Wistar rats to aqueous extract of *D. guineense* stem bark for a period of twelve weeks (3 months) led to significant and time-dependent increases in their body weight and high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-C) level ($p < 0.05$), but it did not significantly alter the total protein concentration ($p > 0.05$). In addition, the extract treatment significantly and time-dependently reduced the levels of total cholesterol (TC), triacylglycerol (TG), low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C), very low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (VLDL-C), atherogenic index of*

***Abu, O.D., Awhin, E.P. and Ekugum, E.**

plasma (AIP), and atherogenic coefficient (AC) ($p < 0.05$). However, the marked reduction in cardiac risk ratio (CRR) was not time-dependent. These results indicate that the medicinal plant stem bark applied over a long period of time can effectively manage disease conditions, which hallmarks are hypercholesterolemia and hypertriglyceridemia.

INTRODUCTION

Herbal medicine has gained wide acceptance, globally (Maunder *et al.*, 2020; Negi *et al.*, 2021). The growing interest in the exploitation of plants for medicinal purposes, especially in Africa, has increased tremendously (Thyagarajan *et al.*, 2002). Medicinal plants have proven health benefits (Abu *et al.*, 2020, 2021a, 2021b, 2022a and 2022b).

Dialium guineense (Velvet Tamarind) is a tall, tropical, fruit-bearing tree which belongs to the *Leguminosae* family (Abu *et al.*, 2023a). It has small, typically grape-sized edible fruits with brown hard inedible shells. It grows in dense forests in Africa along the southern edge of the Sahel and it can be found in West African countries such as Ghana where it is known as “Yoyi”, Sierra Leone, Senegal, Guinea-Bissau and Nigeria where it is known as “Awin” or “Igbaru” in Yoruba, “Icheku” in Igbo, “Tsamiyarkurm” in Hausa and “Amughen” in Edo (Abu *et al.*, 2023b). The bark and leaves have medicinal properties, and are used against several diseases. Extracts of the plant are reported to be rich in important phytochemicals (Abu *et al.*, 2023c).

As a muscular organ the heart pumps blood through the blood vessels of the circulatory system (Benson *et al.*, 2001). Blood provides the

animal’s body with oxygen/nutrients, and facilitate the removal of metabolic wastes. In humans, it is located in the middle compartment of the chest between the lungs (Guyton and Hall, 2006; Moore *et al.*, 2009; Taber and Venes, 2009). The heart is effectively a syncytium, a meshwork of cardiac muscle cells interconnected by contiguous cytoplasmic bridges (Maton *et al.*, 1993; DuBose, 1996; MacDonald, 2009). Drug-induced cardiac injury is becoming an increasingly important concern, since it constitutes serious risk to human health (Dessalvi *et al.*, 2018). Cardiac dysfunction may lead to heart failure, myocardial ischemia, arrhythmias, hypertension, myocarditis, pericarditis, and thromboembolism (Colombo *et al.*, 2013). This study evaluated cardiovascular disease risk factors in normal Wistar rats on prolonged exposure to aqueous stem bark extract of *Dialium guineense*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Chemicals

All chemicals and reagents used in this study were of analytical grade and they were products of Sigma-Aldrich Ltd. (USA).

Collection of Plant Material

The stems of *D. guineense* were collected from Auchi, Edo State, Nigeria, and authenticated at

*Abu, O.D., Awhin, E.P. and Ekugum, E.

the herbarium of the University of Benin, Nigeria, domiciled in the Department of Plant Biology and Biotechnology (No. UBHb330).

Extract Preparation

The plant stem bark was washed and shade-dried at room temperature for 30 days and thereafter pulverized. Exactly 500 g of the ground plant material was macerated in distilled water (5 L) with intermittent stirring for 72 h. The resultant extract was filtered with a muslin cloth and consequently freeze-dried via lyophilization (Abu *et al.*, 2022a, b, c, d).

Experimental Animals

Male albino rats (Wistar strain, n = 10) weighing between 150 and 180 g (mean weight = 165 ± 15 g) were bought from the Department of Anatomy, University of Benin, Nigeria. The rats were housed in metal cages under standard laboratory conditions (25 °C, 60 ± 5 % humidity, and 12-h light/12-h dark cycle). They were acclimatized for fourteen days before commencement of the study, and had free access to feed and water.

Experimental Design

The experimental rats were divided into two groups (5 rats/group): control and observation groups. The observation group rats were administered 1000 mg/kg bwt AEDG stem bark orally for 12 weeks (3 months).

Blood Sample Collection and Preparation

At the end of week-12 of treatment, the rats were euthanized under mild chloroform anaesthesia after an overnight fast. Blood was drawn via

cardiac puncture into heparinized sample bottles and centrifuged at 2000 rpm for 10 min to obtain plasma which was used for biochemical analyses.

Biochemical Analyses

Lipid profile and cardiovascular disease risk parameters were determined in plasma (Friedewald *et al.*, 1972; Lopes-Virella *et al.*, 1977; Reiser *et al.*, 1985; Tietz *et al.*, 1990; Frohlich and Dobiášová, 2003; Abu *et al.*, 2022c).

Data Analysis

Data are expressed as mean \pm standard error of mean (SEM, n = 5). One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was performed using SPSS (version 20). Statistical significance was assumed at $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS

Effect of 12-Week Exposure of Normal Rats to Aqueous Extract of *D. guineense* Stem Bark

As shown in Figures 1 – 6, exposure of normal Wistar rats to aqueous extract of *D. guineense* stem bark for a period of twelve weeks (3 months) led to significant and time-dependent increases in their body weight and HDL-C level ($p < 0.05$), but it did not significantly alter the total protein concentration ($p > 0.05$). In addition, the extract treatment significantly and time-dependently reduced the levels of TC, TG, LDL-C, VLDL-C, AIP, and AC ($p < 0.05$). However, the marked reduction in CRR was not time-dependent.

Figure 1: Body Weight of Rat

Figure 2: Effect of AEDG Stem Bark on Plasma Total Protein and Cholesterol Concentrations

***Abu, O.D., Awhin, E.P. and Ekugum, E.**

Figure 3: Effect of AEDG Stem Bark on Plasma Triacylglycerol and Very Low-Density Lipoprotein Cholesterol Concentrations

Figure 4: Effect of AEDG Stem Bark on Plasma High-Density Lipoprotein Cholesterol and Low-Density Lipoprotein Cholesterol Concentrations

*Abu, O.D., Awhin, E.P. and Ekugum, E.

Figure 5: Effect of AEDG Stem Bark on Atherogenic Index of Plasma and Atherogenic Coefficient

Figure 6: Effect of AEDG Stem Bark on Cardiovascular Disease Risk Ratio in the Rats

DISCUSSION

Globally, a significant cause of morbidity and mortality are cardiovascular diseases (CVDs). Improper management of risk factors of CVDs can lead to deleterious consequences. Risk

factors refer to modifiable biological characteristics (serum lipids, other fractions, blood pressure, blood glucose and insulin, and thrombogenic factors, among others) but can also be applied to behavior, such as smoking or physical inactivity. They are used for two main purposes: detection of individuals and populations at risk of CVD, and determination of

***Abu, O.D., Awhin, E.P. and Ekugum, E.**

the causes of CVD. A risk factor may be useful as a predictor of risk without being casually linked to pathogenic mechanisms. This study evaluated cardiovascular disease risk factors in normal Wistar rats exposed to aqueous stem bark extract of *Dialium guineense* for a prolonged period of 12 weeks (3 months). The results showed that exposure of normal Wistar rats to aqueous extract of *D. guineense* stem bark for a period of twelve weeks led to significant and time-dependent increases in their body weight and HDL-C level, but it did not significantly alter the total protein concentration. In addition, the extract treatment significantly and time-dependently reduced the levels of TC, TG, LDL-C, VLDL-C, AIP, and AC. However, the marked reduction in CRR was not time-dependent. Studies have demonstrated the relationships between lipid profiles and CVD, which include heart attacks and strokes. Elevated levels of conventional lipid indices, such as total cholesterol, low-density lipoprotein cholesterol, and triacylglycerols, are positively correlated with increased risk of CVD incidence, as are decreased levels of high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (Gu *et al.*, 2019; Sun *et al.*, 2019). The connections between TC, LDL-C, HDL-C, and the incidence of CVD-related death risk had also been reported (Curb *et al.*, 2004; Zhong *et al.*, 2020). Because assessment of the correlation between dyslipidemia, CVD events and all-cause mortality using a single lipid score has its drawbacks, some studies proposed that measuring apolipoprotein B (ApoB) should be

the first priority in clinical practice, along with lipid ratios and lipoproteins, which contribute additional clinical value (Walldius and Jungner, 2006; Sierra-Johnson *et al.*, 2009). Surprisingly, some studies have revealed that derived lipid indices, such as computed lipid ratio and apolipoproteins, may have a CVD predictive value similar to traditional lipid indices (Yokokawa *et al.*, 2011). The results of this study have further strengthened the observation that extracts of *D. guineense* are effective in ameliorating complications of some diseases (Abu and Onoagbe, 2019; Abu *et al.*, 2022e – o; Abu *et al.*, 2023d). The biological/pharmacological effects of plant extracts/plant-derived materials have been linked to the presence of important bioactive compounds (Abu *et al.*, 2015; Abu *et al.*, 2017; Ebhohon *et al.*, 2019a and 2019b; Okpiabhele *et al.*, 2018; Abu *et al.*, 2020; Omoregie *et al.*, 2020; Abu *et al.*, 2021a and 2021b).

CONCLUSION

Dialium guineense has been indicated in the treatment of various health ailments in traditional system of medicine. The stem bark extract shows potential for the management of lipid-associated diseases, especially when used for a prolonged duration.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors wish to specially appreciate the laboratory staff of the Department of Biochemistry, Faculty of Life Sciences,

***Abu, O.D., Awhin, E.P. and Ekugum, E.**

University of Benin, for providing technical support for this work.

REFERENCES

- Abu, O.D., Awhin, E.P. and Ohikhuare, F. (2023a). Effect of Methanol Fraction of Ethanol Extract of *Dialium guineense* Stem Bark on Cardiovascular Disease Risk Factors in Diabetic Rats. *Journal of Biology and Medicine*, **4** (1): 128. Retrieved from: <https://gnoscience.com/uploads/journals/articles/766731346684>
- Abu, O.D., Awhin, E.P. and Iyare, H.E. (2023b). Assessment of Renal Function in Diabetic Wistar Rats Treated with Ethanol Extract of *Cucumis sativus*. **4** (1): 59-64.
- Abu, O.D., Ojo, I. and Ezike, T.V. (2023c). Methanol Fraction of Ethanol Extract of *Dialium guineense* Stem Bark Mitigates STZ-Induced Oxidative Stress in Rat Liver. *Biomedical Journal of Scientific and Technical Research*, **51** (2): 42594 – 42600. DOI: 10.26717/BJSTR.2023.51.008085
- Abu, O.D., Awhin, E.P. and Ifekwe, J.C. (2023d). Liver Function Status of Diabetic Wistar Rats Treated with Ethanol Extract of *Cucumis sativus* Fruit. *Biomedical Journal of Scientific and Technical Research*, **51**(2): 42440 – 42445. DOI: 10.26717/BJSTR.2023.51.
- Abu O.D., Umar A-B. and Eiremiokhae C.O. (2022a). Investigation of the cardioprotective capacity of aqueous extract of *Icacina trichanta* leaves in rats exposed to CCl₄. *Journal of Genetics and Cell Biology*, **6** (1): 322 – 328. <https://www.scitcentral.com/article/26/2928/Investigation-of-the-Cardioprotective-Capacity-of-Aqueous-Extract-of-Icacina-Trichanta-Leaves-in-Rats-Exposed-to-CCl4>
- Abu, O.D., Ngedaa, OS and Osarhenomase, E.G. (2022b). Effect of Extracts of *Dialium guineense* Stem Bark on Lipid peroxidation Index and Histological Changes in Kidneys of Normal Rats. *Forensic Medicine*, **4** (2): 23 – 29. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.33545/27074447.2022.v4.i2a.52>
- Abu, O.D., Odagwe U.B. and Ojo A.U. (2022c). Cardiotoxicity of Ethanol Extract of *Dialium guineense* Stem Bark in Rats. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Life Sciences*, **8** (11): 34 – 39. https://www.wjpls.org/admin/assets/article_issue/86102022/1667196280.pdf
- Abu, O.D., Okuo, A.V. and Osemwota, O.F. (2022d). Extracts of *Dialium guineense*

***Abu, O.D., Awhin, E.P. and Ekugum, E.**

Stem Bark Ameliorates CCl₄-induced Oxidative Stress in Liver of Wistar Rats. *Biomedical Journal of Scientific and Technical Research*, 46 (2): 37297 – 37301.

saponins and Tannins of *Dialium guineense* Stem Bark in the Amelioration of Carbon Tetrachloride- Induced Renal Oxidative Stress. *SAU Science-Tech. Journal*, 7 (1): 42 - 50.

Abu, O.D., Eromosele, A.I. and Osarhenomase, E.G. (2022e). Effect of Extracts of *Dialium guineense* Stem Bark on Lipid Profile and CCl₄- Induced Histological Changes in Liver of Wistar Rats. *International Journal of Lipids*, 1 (1): 22 – 27.

Retrieved from:
<https://journals.sau.edu.ng/index.php/sjbas>

Abu, O.D., Iyare, H.E. and Ogboi, K.U. (2022f). Antioxidant Property of Total Saponins and Tannins of *Dialium guineense* Stem Bark in Rats Hearts Exposed to CCl₄. *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology and Toxicology*, 3(3): 1–4.

Abu, O.D. and Ikponmwosa-Eweka, O. (2022i). Potential of Total Saponins and Tannins Isolated from the stem bark of *Dialium guineense* in the Amelioration of Kidney Dysfunction Caused by CCl₄. *Journal of Basic and Applied Medical Sciences*, 2 (1): 1 – 6.

Retrieved from:
<http://www.escientificresearch.com>

Abu, O.D. and Ikponmwosa-Eweka, O. (2022j). Potential of Extracts of *Dialium guineense* Stem Bark in the Mitigation of Carbon Tetrachloride-induced Renal Oxidative Stress. *BIU Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*, 7 (1): 62 – 69. Retrieved from:

Abu, O.D., Iyare, H.E. and Omoruyi, I.J. (2022g). Toxic Responses of the Blood of Rats Exposed to Aqueous Extract of *Dialium guineense* Stem Bark. *FUDMA Journal of Science*, 7 (2): 117 – 120. <https://doi.org/10.33003/fjs-2023-0702-1713>

<http://www.biu.edu.ng/blog-post/potential-extracts-dialium-guineense-stem-bark-mitigation-carbon-tetrachloride-renal-oxidative-stress>

Abu, O.D. and Ikponmwosa-Eweka, O. (2022h). Evaluation of the Potential of Total

Abu, O.D. and Onoagbe, I.O. (2019). Biochemical effect of aqueous extract of *Dialium guineense* stem bark on oxidative status of normal Wistar rats. *International*

***Abu, O.D., Awhin, E.P. and Ekugum, E.**

Journal of Clinical Biology and Biochemistry, **1** (2): 15 – 18. DOI: 10.33545/26646188.2019.v1.i2a.10

Rats. *Journal of Pharmaceutical and Bio-Medical Sciences*, **2** (9): 353 – 357. <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijpbms/v2-i9-04>

Abu, O.D., Alegun, O. and Ifekwe, J.C. (2023d). Renal Oxidative Status in Diabetic Wistar Rats Administered Methanol Fraction of Ethanol Extract of *Dialium guineense*. *Medical and Clinical Case Reports Journal*, **1**(1): 1 – 13.

Abu, O.D., Onoagbe, I.O., and Ohikhuare, F. (2022m). Nephrotoxic Evaluation of Ethanol Stem Bark Extract of *Dialium guineense* in Normal Wistar Rats. *International Journal of Forensic Medicine*, **4** (2): 19 – 22.

Retrieved from: <https://urfpublishers.com/journal/case-reports>

Abu, O.D., Osagie, A.O. and Kolawole, O.M. (2022n). Ameliorative Effect of Extracts of *Dialium guineense* Stem Bark in CCL4-Induced Kidney Dysfunction in Wistar Rats. *Biokemistri*, **34** (2): 34310 – 34316.

Abu, O.D., Odagwe, U.B. and Ojo, A.U. (2022j). Cardiotoxicity of Ethanol Extract of *Dialium guineense* Stem Bark in Rats. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Life Sciences*, **8** (11): 34 – 39. Retrieved from: <https://www.wjpls.org>

Abu, O.D., Umar, A-B. and Adekanle, E. (2022o). Cardiotoxic Effect of Aqueous Extract of *Dialium guineense* Stem Bark in Wistar Rats. *East African Scholars Journal of Agriculture and Life Sciences*. **5** (9): 167 – 172. DOI: 10.36349/easjals.2022.v05i09.002

Abu, O.D., Onoagbe, I.O., and Ekugum, E. (2022k). Hepatotoxicity of Graded Doses of Ethanol Extract of *Dialium guineense* Stem Bark in Wistar Rats. *Journal of Pharmaceutical and Bio-Medical Sciences*, **2**(9): 347-352. <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijpbms/v2-i9-04>

Abu, O.D., Imafidon, K.E. and Obayuwana, O. (2020). Effect of aqueous extract of *Anacardium occidentale* leaves on blood glucose level and lipid profile of diabetic rats. *Global Scientific Journal*, **8**(10): 977–987. Retrieved from: <https://globalscientificjournal.com>

Abu, O.D., Onoagbe, I.O., and Ekugum, E. (2022l). Nephrotoxic Evaluation of Aqueous Stem Bark Extract of *Dialium guineense* in Normal Wistar

***Abu, O.D., Awhin, E.P. and Ekugum, E.**

- Abu, O.D., Imafidon, K.E. and Iribhogbe, M.E. (2015). Biochemical effect of aqueous leaf extract of *icacina trichanta* Oliv. on urea, creatinine and kidney oxidative status in CCl₄-induced Wistar rats. *Nigerian Journal of Life Sciences*, **5** (1): 85 - 89. DOI: 10.52417/njls.v5i1.211
- Abu, O.D., Imafidon, K.E. and Obayuwana, H.O. (2021a). Nephrotoxic and *in vivo* antioxidant effects of *citrullus lanatus* seed extract. *Biomedical Journal of Science and Technical Research*, **33**(5): 26281–26286. DOI: 10.26717/BJSTR.2021.33.005473
- Abu, O.D., Imafidon, K.E., Obayuwana, H.O. and Okuofu, E.D. (2017). Phytochemical, proximate and metal content analysis of *citrullus lanatus* (watermelon) seeds. *FUDMA Journal of Sciences*, **2** (2): 153 - 156.
- Retrieved from: <http://fjs.fudutsinma.edu.ng/index.php/fjs/archive>
- Abu, O.D., Olude, O.M. and Obayuwana, H.O. (2021b). Effect of methanol extract of *Citrullus lanatus* seed on hematological profile and tissue histology of normal Wistar rats. *Advance Research Journal of Medical and Clinical Science*, **7**(7): 608–615. Retrieved from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8094133/>
- Benson, J.M., Tibbetts, B.M. and Thrall, K.D. (2001). Uptake, tissue distribution, and fate of inhaled carbon tetrachloride: comparison of rat, mouse, and hamster. *Inhalation Toxicology*, **13**: 207 – 217. DOI: 10.1080/08958370150502449
- Colombo, A., Meroni, C.A., Cipolla, C.M. and Cardinale, D. (2013). Managing cardiotoxicity of chemotherapy. *Current Treatment Options in Cardiovascular Medicine*, **15**(4): 410-424. DOI: 10.1007/s11936-013-0248-3
- Curb, J.D., Abbott, R.D., Rodriguez, B.L., Masaki, K., Popper, J., Chen, R. and Yano, K. (2004). Prospective association between low and high total and low-density lipoprotein cholesterol and coronary heart disease in elderly men. *Journal of the American Geriatrics Society*. **52** (12): 1975 - 1980. DOI: 10.3923/ajbs.2018.138.144
- Dessalvi, C.C., Deidda, M., Mele, D., Bassareo, P. and Esposito, R. (2018). Chemotherapy-induced cardiotoxicity: new insights into mechanisms, monitoring, and prevention. *Journal of Cardiovascular Medicine*, **19**(7): 315-323. DOI: 10.2459/JCM.00000000000006

- DuBose, T.J. (1996). *Fetal Sonography*, pp. 263–274; Philadelphia: WB Saunders
- Fennema, O. (2008). *Fennema's Food Chemistry*. CRC Press Taylor & Francis. Pp. 454–455.
- Ebhohon, S.O., Ibeh, R.C., Ejiofor, U.E., Abu, O.D. and Chibueze, F.C. (2019a). Aqueous extract of *Hibiscus Sabdariffa* ameliorates cadmium-induced liver and kidney injuries in male Wistar rats. *Journal of Society for Experimental Biology of Nigeria*, **19** (1): 55 – 59. Retrieved from: <https://ojs.klobexjournals.com>
- Ebhohon, S.O., Ibeh, R.C., Ejiofor, U.E., Abu, O.D. and Osegenna, S.C. (2019b). Hepato- and nephro-protective effects of methanol extract of *Citrullus lanatus* rind in Wistar rats fed with used motor engine oil contaminated feed. *FUDMA Journal of Sciences*, **3** (4): 246 – 250. Retrieved from: <http://fjs.fudutsinma.edu.ng/index.php/fjs/archive>
- Friedewald, W.T., Levy, R.I. and Fredrickson, D.S. (1972). Estimation of the concentration of low-density lipoprotein cholesterol in plasma, without use of the preparative ultracentrifuge. *Clinical Chemistry*, **18** (6): 499 - 502.
- Frohlich, J. and Dobiášová, M. (2003). Fractional Esterification Rate of Cholesterol and Ratio of Triglycerides to HDL-Cholesterol Are Powerful Predictors of Positive Findings on Coronary Angiography. *Clinical Chemistry*. **49** (11): 1873 – 1880. DOI: 10.1373/clinchem.2003.022558
- Gu, X., Li, Y., Chen, S., Yang, X., Liu, F., Li, Y. and Gu, D. (2019). Association of lipids with ischemic and hemorrhagic stroke: a prospective cohort study among 267 500 Chinese. *Stroke*. **50** (12): 3376 - 3384.
- Guyton, A.C. and Hall, J.E. (2006). *Textbook of Medical Physiology* (11th ed.). Philadelphia: Elsevier Saunder. Pp. 24.
- Lopes-Virella, M.F., Stone, P., Ellis, S. and Colwell, J.A. (1977). Cholesterol determination in high-density lipoproteins separated by three different methods. *Clinical Chemistry*, **23** (5): 882 - 884. Retrieved from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>
- MacDonald, M. (2009). *Your Body: The Missing Manual*. Sebastopol, CA: Pogue Press. Pp.40.
- Maton, A., Jean, H., Charles, W.M., Susan, J., Maryanna, Q.W., David, L.J. and Wright, D. (1993). *Human Biology and Health*.
- *Abu, O.D., Awhin, E.P. and Ekugum, E.**

Englewood Cliffs, New Jersey, USA:
Prentice Hall.

Retrieved from:
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>

Moore, K.L., Dalley, A.F. and Agur, A.M.R. (2009). Clinically oriented anatomy. Wolters Kluwer Health/Lippincott William & Wilkins. Pp. 127 – 173.

Sierra-Johnson, J., Fisher, R.M., Romero-Corral, A., Somers, V.K., Lopez-Jimenez, F., Öhrvik, J. and Hamsten, A. (2009). Concentration of apolipoprotein B is comparable with the apolipoprotein B/apolipoprotein AI ratio and better than routine clinical lipid measurements in predicting coronary heart disease mortality: findings from a multi-ethnic US population. *European Heart Journal*. 30 (6): 710 - 717.

Okpiabhele, A.O., Nwanze, E.A.C. and Abu, O.D., (2018). Therapeutic Potential of Virgin Coconut Oil in Ameliorating Diabetes Mellitus and Hepatotoxicity Using *Rattus Norvegicus* as Case Study. *Asian Journal of Biological Sciences*, **11** (3): 138 – 144.

Sun, L., Clarke, R., Bennett, D., Guo, Y., Walters, R.G., Hill, M. and China Kadoorie Biobank Collaborative Group (2019). Causal associations of blood lipids with risk of ischemic stroke and intracerebral hemorrhage in Chinese adults. *Nature Medicine*. 25 (4): 569 - 574.

Omoregie, F.O., Abu, O.D. and Olude, O.M. (2020). Ameliorative effects of aqueous leaf extract of *Annona muricata* on cyanide-induced toxicity in New Zealand Rabbits. *Journal of Bioinnovation*, **9** (6): 1532 – 1540. <https://doi.org/10.46344/JBINO.2020.v09i06.38>

Taber, C.W. and Venes, D. (2009). Taber's cyclopedic medical dictionary. Davies F.A. Co. Pp. 1018 – 1023.

Reiser, R., Probstfield, J.L., Silvers, A., Scott, L.W., Shorney, M.L., Wood, R.D., O'Brien, B.C., Gotto, A.M. and Insull, W. (1985). Plasma lipid and lipoprotein response of humans to beef fat, coconut oil and safflower oil. *American Journal of Clinical Nutrition*, **42** (2):190 - 197. DOI: 10.1093/ajcn/42.2.190

Taskinen, M.R., Barter, P.J., Ehnholm, C., Sullivan, D.R., Mann, K., Simes, J. and FIELD Study Investigators. (2010). Ability of traditional lipid ratios and apolipoprotein ratios to predict

***Abu, O.D., Awhin, E.P. and Ekugum, E.**

cardiovascular risk in people with type 2 diabetes. *Diabetologia*, 53: 1846 - 1855.

prospective cohort studies.
European Journal of Preventive Cardiology. 27 (11): 1187 - 1203.

Tietz, N.W., Finley, P.R. and Pruden, E.L. (1990). Clinical Guide to Laboratory Tests. 2nd Edition, W.B. Saunders, Philadelphia. Pp. 304 - 306.

Walldius, G. and Jungner, I. (2006). The apoB/apoA-I ratio: a strong, new risk factor for cardiovascular disease and a target for lipid-lowering therapy—a review of the evidence. *Journal of Internal Medicine*. 259 (5): 493 - 519.

World Health Organization (2009). Medicines: Safety of medicines-adverse drug reactions.

Yokokawa, H., Yasumura, S., Tanno, K., Ohsawa, M., Onoda, T., Itai, K. and Okayama, A. (2011). Serum low-density lipoprotein to high-density lipoprotein ratio as a predictor of future acute myocardial infarction among men in a 2.7-year cohort study of a Japanese northern rural population. *Journal of Atherosclerosis and Thrombosis*. 18 (2): 89 - 98.

Zhong, G.C., Huang, S.Q., Peng, Y., Wan, L., Wu, Y.Q.L., Hu, T.Y. and Hao, F.B. (2020). HDL- C is associated with mortality from all causes, cardiovascular disease and cancer in a J-shaped dose-response fashion: a pooled analysis of 37

***Abu, O.D., Awhin, E.P. and Ekugum, E.**